

The Development Of Supplementary Worksheet For Principle Of Molarity Concept For Virtual Laboratory Simulation In Grade 12 Laboratory Senior High School Students In GC 2: General Chemistry At Cavite State University-CCAT Campus A.Y. 2024-2025

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Abstract

This study utilized developmental research design to construct a supplementary worksheet for the virtual laboratory simulation in principle of molarity. 30 Grade 12 respondents from Laboratory Science High School participated in evaluating the efficacy of the supplementary worksheet in accordance with learning outcomes, conceptual understanding, and application of fundamental skills in learning. This study treated its data with descriptive statistics and item analysis. Research findings revealed that out of 22 questions in the supplementary worksheet, 81.82% of questions are rejected, 9.09% are revised, and 9.09% are retained; this indicates that the supplementary worksheet is too easy for the respondents. However, based on the feedback of the respondents, the worksheet was commended as challenging, straightforward, and engaging, as well as the principles of the mole concept being well integrated. Further development of the supplementary worksheet is necessary. In conclusion, supplementary worksheets are great as classroom activities for concept integration and application. Using a virtual laboratory with supplementary worksheets will be helpful in students' self-learning capabilities and motivational learning.

Keywords: Supplementary Worksheets, Principle of Molarity Concept, General Chemistry, Senior High School Students, Virtual Laboratory

Introduction

According to the Department of Education (DepEd), Filipino students' poor academic performance in the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) has shown a five- to six-year lag in their learning competencies (Ines, 2023). For students' low academic performance was the notion of automatic promotion. It was said that, "While it has been denied that automatic promotion is the official policy, the test results showing a huge proportion of students not having

the required competence of the school level they are in is a piece of compelling evidence that this may not be the case." This concludes that the "students are not truly learning, but merely progressing," and "this failure to master basic fundamentals, such as reading, writing, and numeracy; mass promotion, it was said, also caused unintended behavioral issues as students end up lacking in fundamental values, such as hard work, resiliency, teamwork, and respect." These contributing factors affect statistics and

students' motivation in learning mathematics and science. For instance, one of the tools used together with virtual laboratories are supplementary worksheets. It is an instructional tool for the students that consists of a series of questions to guide the students to understand complex ideas and work through the worksheet systematically (Choo et al., 2011). Worksheets that have high level validity and high practicality for the students and are highly recommended by the lecturer can be used as one of the learning materials in the learning process of the students (Kardena & Mawardi, 2021). To conclude, worksheets can develop students' cognitive knowledge and science processing skills (Felitasaria & Rusminib, 2022).

Virtual laboratories are convenient for students, as they can access them anywhere with an internet connection. They are the alternative route when there are restrictions on using traditional laboratories. The interactive simulations and multimedia elements also maintain students' motivation and interest (Asare, 2023). Exhibiting the students in the virtual laboratories will improve their academic performance, as it is reliable in teaching chemistry to the students (Famuwagun & Mohammed, 2020).

For these reasons, the researchers plan to develop a supplementary worksheet to enhance students' academic performance. This supplementary worksheet will help the student to reach their lag in learning competencies and develop their self-learning skills. Educators will use it to fulfill the students' target needs.

Methodology

Description of the Project

The main purpose of the researchers' supplementary worksheet is to provide a worksheet guide for students, specific to senior high school students, to have a guide in manipulating the PhET Colorado, which is a type of virtual laboratory that will help them experience interactive laboratories even without having the actual materials for their experiments. Furthermore, the

researchers' supplementary worksheet will encourage students to explore the vast knowledge of the science subject without limiting themselves because they can now access virtual laboratories as an alternative to traditional laboratories and also engage in a fun and productive simulation while they're learning.

Design and Procedures

This study makes use of developmental research design, which is the systematic study of designing, developing, and evaluating instructional programs, processes, and products that must meet criteria of internal consistency and effectiveness (Rita, R. 1994). The study aims to: (1) develop a supplementary worksheet; (2) administer the worksheet to the respondents; (3) collect the answers of the respondents as data; (4) gather the respondents' feedback about the worksheet; and (5) recommend emendations for the worksheet based on the feedback of the respondents.

Testing and Evaluation

Thirty (30) Grade 12 STEM students from Laboratory Science High School participated in this study as respondents; eleven (11) of them were male and nineteen (19) were female. The target respondents are students in 12th grade because they are the most flexible and available for the study that the researchers are conducting. Furthermore, students can understand and synthesize the information presented in the supplementary worksheet. It is related to the topic they discussed before as well.

Data Analysis

The main objective of this research study was to develop a supplementary worksheet for a virtual laboratory simulation of the molarity concept. With this in mind, the study took the necessary steps in order to successfully develop the product in accordance with the learning outcomes of grade 12 students. As well as the evaluation of their feedback regarding the product using a survey questionnaire. It is crucial to determine the deficiency of the supplementary worksheet for future researchers to identify what needs to be

done in order to further develop the supplementary worksheet. Therefore, the methods and techniques to be used for data analysis are critical for the success of the study. To determine the complexity of the supplementary worksheet, the researchers will utilize item analysis and calculate the weighted percentage, difficulty index, and discrimination index. It will determine which items need to be retained, revised, or rejected. Additionally, the survey questionnaire will be treated using descriptive statistics. As for the short response part of the survey, cross-tabulation will be utilized.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical considerations in research papers are crucial in evaluating the moral implications of the researchers' decisions and actions. It is significant to be ethically considerate, as it enhances the validity of the research findings and safeguards human rights and the well-being of study participants. In the context of the current research study, ethical considerations will be meticulously observed throughout the data-gathering procedures.

The target respondents of this study were the Grade 12 students enrolled at the Laboratory Science High School, which meant that most of the participants were minors; hence, it is imperative that the researchers get permission from the university, the high school, and their class advisor for consent to having them as respondents.

The researchers intend to carry out data collection activities following the conclusion of official school hours. It is anticipated that the duration of this data gathering will not exceed three hours. During the data gathering sessions, photos will be captured for recording and evidence purposes. After the collection, the data will be treated following Republic Act No. 10173, generally known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012. All the personal information gathered will be treated for the sole purpose of contacting them regarding their response. The respondents' names will be replaced by pseudonyms, and their emails will be deleted once the study is concluded. Additionally, the photos to be attached to the paper will ensure to not

include facial features that will reveal their identity.

This study will ensure that all of its data is stored properly and kept in secrecy. Personal information will be confidential for compliance with the law. The researchers will maintain their professionalism and conduct throughout the research study.

Result and Discussion

How to develop a supplementary worksheet for a Principles of Molarity Concept virtual laboratory simulation?

The researchers develop a worksheet by providing an image tutorial wherein it has steps and indications that must be followed to be able to manipulate the laboratory simulation and to answer the questions contained within the worksheet. The researchers also emphasized the graphic format because it needed to be aesthetically pleasing to hold the attention of the respondents.

Furthermore, the supplementary worksheet has three (3) activities that measure the respondents problem-solving abilities and scientific reasoning. The first and second activities in the worksheet measure the students critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and scientific reasoning, where they need to answer all the questions and justify their answers. The third activity in the worksheet also measures their critical thinking, where they need to solve a puzzle. It contains a set of questions they need to answer to solve the puzzle in the activity. After completing the worksheet, they made the respondents answer it and provided them with a survey question that needed to be answered in order to determine the improvements that the supplementary worksheet needed to be more helpful as a guide.

How can the assessment of conceptual comprehension, problem-solving abilities, and scientific reasoning be used to measure the students' learning outcomes on the supplemental worksheet?

This study will use a difficulty index to analyze and interpret the research data.

The item is very difficult if the index range is between 0.00 - 0.20. The item is difficult if the index range is between 0.21 - 0.40. Easy if the index range is between 0.61 - 0.80. The item is very easy if the index range is between 0.81 - 1.00.

Consequently, the study will use a discrimination index. It is a poor item if the index range is 0.19 and below; the item should be rejected or is needed to be revised. It is a marginal item if the index range is 0.20–0.29; the item will be subjected for revision. It is a reasonably good item if the index range is 0.30–0.39; the item is considered a reasonably good item but possible for improvement. It is a very good item if the index range is 0.40 and above; it should be retained.

The item will be retained if the difficulty index is within the 0.26 and 0.75 range and if the difficulty index is within 0.20 and above. The item will be revised if the difficulty index is within 0.26 and 0.75 and not within that range and if the difficulty index is within 0.19 below and 0.20 above. The item will be rejected if the difficulty index is not within the 0.26 and 0.75 range and if the difficulty index is within 0.19 below.

Through the item analysis of all the 22 questions of the worksheet by the researchers, it was shown that all the questions except item 5 are considered poor items due to the fact that their index range is below 0.19, which indicates that they should be rejected or are needed to be revised. Item 5, which is considered a reasonably good item, will be retained because its difficulty index is within the 0.26 and 0.75 range and the discrimination index is within the 0.20 and above range. Item 8 will be revised because its difficulty index is not within 0.26 and 0.75 and its discrimination index is above 0.20. Item 10 will also be revised because its difficulty index is between 0.26 and 0.75 and its discrimination index is below 19. All the other items are rejected because their difficulty indexes are not within 0.26 and 0.75 and their discrimination is within 0.19 and below.

What are the students' feedback to be evaluated on the supplementary worksheet in terms of:

Clarity of Instruction

The data shows that most students understood instructions well, followed them effortlessly in the virtual laboratory, and believed language and grammar helped them understand. They did not get overwhelmed by the instructions and found them clear and easy to understand.

Engagement of Activities

The students found the supplementary worksheet activities interesting, encouraging them to learn about the Principle of Molarity. They found the activities hands-on, challenging, and satisfied after answering the questions. Some still found them difficult.

Content Complexity

Most respondents believe the worksheet items can be answered with proper knowledge, and the concept of Molarity is used. They feel stimulated and challenged, and find the concept fair. However, they have mixed feedback on prior knowledge.

Virtual Laboratory Integration

The majority of respondents found the virtual laboratory simulation easy to navigate, interactive, and useful. They were encouraged to explore and experiment, and their understanding of the Molarity concept improved through the simulation.

What are the recommended developments on the supplementary worksheet based on the results of the research data?

Researchers collected data through survey questionnaires to improve a supplementary worksheet on Molarity. Respondents appreciated the clear instructions, interactivity, visual appeal, and engaging questions. They found the Molarity concept challenging but comprehensible. The worksheet's integration of a virtual laboratory simulation was particularly insightful.

Some respondents wanted more topics from Chemistry and Biology. Recommendations included removing answer keys, improving questions, adding visual aids, addressing minor errors, and improving simulation usage. Most respondents were satisfied with the worksheet.

Table 1: Summary of the feedbacks

Survey Question	Feedback Summary
Do you have any recommendations for improving the supplementary worksheet?	The worksheet will be improved by removing answer keys, adding visual aids, addressing language and typography errors, and adding more topics from Chemistry or other science branches.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

(1) To help the target respondents better understand the molarity concept, the researchers have created an additional worksheet with a variety of exercises that effectively makes use of the PhET Colorado Simulation Application. (2) The researchers used PhET Colorado Simulation to create a worksheet with 22 questions, but results found it too simple for respondents, with 81.82% rejected, 9.09% revised, and 9.09% retained. (3) The survey questionnaire evaluated students, revealing clear instructions, interactive worksheets, challenging yet manageable questions, and successful integration of virtual laboratory simulation. (4) Respondents suggested adding chemistry and other science topics, enhancing the questions, correcting typographical and grammatical errors on a worksheet, and incorporating new simulations for upcoming science-related activities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made by the feedback and comments of the students through a survey: **(1) Removing the Answer Key:** For future researchers, removing the answer key at the end of every activity will help the students to rely more on their answers. This will help them to improve their critical thinking and problem-solving skills as they use their cognitive skills to solve the questions. **(2) Grammar and Typographical Errors:** Double check the grammar and the typographical errors of every question and activity. This will allow the students to have a better understanding of the questions and be able to answer all the questions with ease. **(3) Laboratory Simulation:** There are a lot of laboratory simulations that future researchers can find on the internet. Look for other simulations that are easy to understand and manipulate to help the students answer the worksheet. **(4) Branches of Science:** In making supplementary worksheets, use different branches of science, such as physics, biology, or chemistry, to have broad topics that future researchers can use in the Worksheet. **(5) Improvement of the Activities:** Adding more activities and improving the visual aids of the worksheet can help the students to improve their academic performance and increase their self-esteem in answering.

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